

"A Guide to Medicinal Plants: Natural Remedies for Health & Wellness"

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English Name	Scientific Name	Family	Native
Papaya	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Caricaceae	Mexico, Costa Rica
Golden Shower tree	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Fabaceae	India, Malaysia
Red betel	<i>Piper crocatum Ruiz & Pav</i>	Piperaceae	Peru, South America
Chebulic myrobalan	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Combretaceae	Southern Asia, India, Nepal
Indian bael	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Rutaceae	India, Nepal, Pakistan
Coconut	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Arecaceae	Southeast Asia, India
Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Sothern China, Nigeria, Nigeria
Aloe vera	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i>	Asphodelaceae	Arabian Peninsula, Australia
Ajwain	<i>Trachysperm ammi</i>	Apiaceae	Egypt, Pakistan, Afghanistan
Amla	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Phyllanthaceae	India, Soth Asia
Senna leaf	<i>Senna alexandrina</i>	Leguminaceae	Northern Africa, Arabia
Liquorice	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Fabaceae	West Asia, North Africa, Europe
Water lily	<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i>	Nymphaceae	North America
Bahera	<i>Terminalia belerica</i>	Combretaceae	India, China, Malayasia
Cinnamon	<i>Cinnamom verum</i>	Lauraceae	Sri Lanka, India, Myanmar
Swerita	<i>Swerita chirata</i>	Gentianaceae	Kashmir, Bhutan
Garlic	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	North-Eastern Iran, South Asia
Chicory	<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Asteraceae	North Africa, Western Asia
Black catechu	<i>Senegalia catechu</i>	Fabaceae	Pakistan, China, Thailand
True cardamom	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>	Zingiberaceae	Sothern India, Sri Lanka

Ashok	<i>Saraca indica</i>	Fabaceae	Soth Asia, Western Myanmar
Nut grass or Mutha	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Cyperaceae	Africa, central Europe, Asia
Common fumitory	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	Papaveraceae	UK
Green chiretta	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Acanthaceae	India, Sri Lanka
Gray aristolochiifolia	<i>Smilax aristalochaefolia</i>	Smilacaceae	Mexico, Central America
Fennel	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Apiaceae	Southern Europe, US
Asshogondha	<i>Withania somnifer</i>	Solanaceae	Africa, Middle East
Kadamba	<i>Neolamarckia cadamba</i>	Rubiaceae	Indian subcontinent, South Asia
Common grape vine	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Vitaceae	Europe, North Africa, West Asia
Barberry	<i>Berberis vulgaris</i>	Berberidaceae	Southern Europe, Northwest Africa
Gum Arabic tree	<i>Acacia arabica</i>	Leguminosae	Western Asia, Africa, India
Mulberry	<i>Morus alba</i>	Moraceae	Northern China
Centella Asiatica	<i>Centella Asiatica</i>	Apiaceae	Asia, Africa, China, Indonesia
Jasmine	<i>Jasminum sambac</i>	Oleaceae	Africa, Australia, Asia
Noni	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Southeast Asia, Australia
Dandelion	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	Asteraceae	Europe, North America
Pomegranate	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Punicaceae	Middle East, India
Nettle	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	Urticaceae	Asia, North America
Horsetail	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Equisetaceae	North America, Asia
Coriander	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Apiaceae	Middle East, South Asia
Fenugreek	<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>	Fabaceae	Mediterranean Sea, Soth Asia
Plantain	<i>Plantago major</i>	Plantaginaceae	Asia, Europe, Iran
Holy Basil	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Lamiaceae	West Africa, Middle East
Meadow saffron	<i>Colchicum autumnale</i>	Colchicaceae	Britain, Europe, North Africa

Shatamuli	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Asparagaceae	Africa, Southeast Asia, Northern Australia
Peepal	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Moraceae	Indo China, Southwest Asia
Goat's Rue	<i>Galega officinalis</i>	Fabaceae	Europe, West Asia, Africa
Soybean	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>	Fabaceae	East Asia
Sugarcane	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>	Poaceae	New Guinea, India
Turmeric	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Zingiberaceae	Southeast Asia, Indian subcontinent
Autumn crocus	<i>Crocus sativus</i>	Iridaceae	Spain, Italy, Greece
Black Seed	<i>Nigella sativa</i>	Ranunculaceae	Europe, North Africa
Bengal currant	<i>Carissa carandas</i>	Apocynaceae	South Africa region